

Small Mistakes in the Beginning: Stanley L. Jaki: Arch-Defender of Christian Civilization of Freedom, and Somewhat Unwitting Obstacle to It?: An American/Gilsonian Perspective

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Before addressing the chief subject of my presentation today, I would like to thank the organizers of this historic World Congress at Cardinal Wyszynski University for extending to me this great honor (that I will always remember) of speaking to you today at this institution founded in celebrate the life of a great priest and hero of Western civilization.

My point of departure for this talk today are two principles that Gilson uses to weave together different intellectual scenarios within *The Unity of Philosophical Experience* into a historical-philosophical thriller about what happens to philosophical teachings

once they leave the abstract thought of philosophers and they, or others, try to put them into practice in the real world. The *first* principle, borrowed from Aristotle, states that small mistakes about first principles made at the start of an intellectual investigation tend to multiply many times over as the study continues¹. The *second* principle, taken from Aristotle and French painter Georges Braque, is that we choose the way we can, not the way we wish.

Gilson then translates this second principle into an observation about the twofold nature of possibility: 1) *conceptually thinkable* in which „we call

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¹ Aristotle, *De Caelo*, book 1, chapter 5, 271b, 8–13, translated by J.L. Stocks, The Clarendon press, Oxford 1922.

possible whatever is not intrinsically impossible – that is, any object whose notion is not self-contradictory”; and, 2) *a humanly doable deed* – what „after being conceived by the mind, can be made to exist in reality” (Gilson, 1958). Next, like a skilled psychologist, Gilson applies these principles to the behavior of people who consider themselves to be philosophers to transform his monograph from a tale of disparate psychological experiments into the powerful, organic, whole book in philosophical history.

Like any good researcher, Gilson realized that philosophy is chiefly a habit of the human soul in which real possibility is determined by the soul’s nature and its faculties as proximate principles of doable deeds in this or that human situation. It is a habit of the acting person; and its chief measure of truth, and failure, is the being of really existing things and a person’s own natural and acquired abilities to generate philosophical actions!

Gilson did not think we measure philosophical success chiefly in terms of abstract, systematic logic, by being able to form a coherent concept or coherently string together non-contradictory judgments. True, such ability is a necessary condition for thinking philosophically; but, as Gilson and St. Thomas had recognized, philosophy, science, is chiefly born of a psychological disposition, habit, of the human soul: sense wonder. And sense wonder is chiefly born in the ability to recognize really doable human deeds.

According to St. Thomas, the chief subject of wonder for the ancient Greek philosophers was not the logical genus: the abstract, conceptual whole and its parts studied by the logician. It was the concrete conceptual whole, the parts of which are proximate generators of action (operational organizations) studied by the physicist and metaphysician. A crucial distinction to understand because all intellectual research essentially involves many failures that experienced researchers understand to be an essential part of specifying a subject matter’s nature, coming more precisely to understand a subject and measure a researcher’s intellectual ability to master it.

Just as not everyone who performs courageous acts necessarily possesses the habit of courage (the psychological disposition of a courageous person), so, not everyone who engages in philosophical, scientific, acts has the psychological disposition, habit, of a philosopher, scientist. Having spent decades of oppression under the yoke of different forms of utopian socialist totalitarian ideologues, this reality about philosophical, scientific, nature, and real versus fictional ability is something that Polish Catholic scholars know quite well. It is also something that Hungarian-born American priest/physicist Stanley L. Jaki knew exceptionally well.

My friend Fr. Jaki was a great admirer of Gilson; so much so that he once called Gilson „possibly the greatest Christian philosopher since Thomas Aquinas”². Like Gilson, and unlike René Descartes, Jaki was convinced that philosophy, sci-

² S.L. Jaki, *Science and Religion: A Primer*, Port Huron, Mich.: Rear View Books, 2004.

ence, are essentially civilizational enterprises requiring the right cultural philosophical, scientific, supports, including intellectual traditions, to be born and continue to progress.

Despite the fact that Jaki was a completely-orthodox priest, an excellent intellectual historian, and a brilliant mathematical physicist, nevertheless, in my opinion, in forming his understanding of modern and contemporary philosophy and science, he made several small mistakes in his induction of first principles that, if not properly addressed, can prove dangerous to reversing the current decline in, and stimulating a strengthening of, Western civilization health, which he sought his work to do.

Precisely, by small mistakes about principles, I refer to several erroneous or badly-framed statements with which Fr. Jaki starts his reasoning regarding the cultural birth of science, which he claims was „born of Christianity”. While this statement might sound arrogant, when properly understood, it is not. Precisely, by the phrase „born of Christianity”, Jaki means that Christian civilization had provided the cultural supports in terms of metaphysical and moral educational traditions and relative political stability to serve as a mid-wife in which the principles and practices of modern and contemporary mathematical physics could be precisely articulated and encouraged to develop. Prior to the advent of European Catholic monastic and cathedral schools, and universities

and relative peace in Europe, none of this had been possible.

Nor was it possible, as Jaki rightly notes, without thirteenth-century doctrinal formulations about the *ex nihilo* Creation of the universe and the *Incar-nation*, which, once and for all, severed the Christian understandings of the universe and human person from the cyclical universe and cyclical notion of time of the ancient Greeks and all other ancient world cultures. Widespread cultural acceptance by Western civilization of these theological teachings for all time thereafter eliminated civilizational dominance in the West, and most of the world, of the cyclical understanding of motion, change, and time, and the moral determinism that had, according to Jaki, been the chief psychological errors, globally, of what he called „the repeated stillbirths of science in all ancient cultures”³.

As evidence of the transformational historical nature of this event generated by the theological teachings of medieval Catholicism, Jaki singles out the initial appearance of Sir Isaac Newton’s first law (the law of inertial motion) to a lecture given by Jean Buridan at the Sorbonne in the 1330s related to Aristotle’s treatise *On the Heavens*. Therein, Buridan linked the origin of such motion to the moment of Creation, at which point, he said God imparted, „a certain quantity of impetus to all celestial bodies, which they keep undiminished because they move in a realm where there is no friction”⁴. Since Jaki

³ S.L. Jaki, *Science and Religion: A Primer*, p. 23.

⁴ S.L. Jaki, *Science and Religion: A Primer*, p. 18.

sees „Buridan’s breakthrough” as providing the theoretical understanding for Newton’s three laws of motion that essentially generated modern mathematical physics, reasonable is for Jaki to credit it with giving birth to modern science, which, strictly speaking, Jaki calls the only „exact science”⁵.

While I agree with Jaki that the advent of Christianity enabled modern mathematical physics to come into being and that he was right when he maintained that Christianity acted as the midwife for the birth of science thus understood, I maintain that he was wrong in thinking that, for the most part, modern physics is exact science and the only science.

I claim that the person who actually was the midwife of the cultural conditions needed for the full birth of modern science was St. Thomas Aquinas, not John Buridan. And St. Thomas was able to achieve this event by coming up with an understanding of science, philosophy, as an organizational psychology: *a habit of animal rationality born of sense wonder located and specified in the animal part of the human soul*, which seeks to understand the nature of organizational wholes!⁶. Without this psychology having started to dominate in the West, as Jaki admits, what he mistakenly calls „exact science” could not have come into being.

To some extent, I agree with Jaki that science derives its exactness from measurement; but I disagree with his claim

that modern and contemporary mathematical physics is a science (since no knowledge that intentionally seeks to separate itself from wisdom can possibly be science); and I disagree with him that: 1) *strictly speaking*, the term „exact science” *is limited to sciences that apply mathematics to matter*; 2) measurement is „application of quantities, or numbers”; 3) „numbers are the specifically-exact notions among all the notions the human mind is capable of forming”; 4) „the various branches of science qualify for being called exact in the measure in which they use numbers connected with measurements”; 5) „Since mathematics does not measure, it is best taken for a form of logic”. 6) „The Greeks of old, whom it is customary to credit with the rise of scientific mentality (...) failed with respect to the most important science, or physics”.

I say „to some extent”. I agree with Jaki that „science derives its exactness from measurement” because, most precisely, *science derives its exactness from evidently-known first principles (evidently-known truths)*; „principles” simply being analogous ways of being „one”, „measures”. Hence, *the science of metaphysics, not the liberal art of logic* (to which, strictly speaking, Jaki says he reduces mathematics), *is the most exact science* („Since mathematics does not measure,” Jaki says, „it is best taken for a form of logic”).

Contra his claim that „numbers are the specifically-exact notions among all

⁵ S.L. Jaki, *Science and Religion: A Primer*, p. 19-23.

⁶ Sancti Thomae Aquinatis, *Summa Theologiae*, Editiones Paulina, Roma 1962, 1, q. 77, a. 3, *respon-*
deo.

⁷ S.L. Jaki, *Science and Religion: A Primer*, p. 4-7 and 19-31.

the notions the human mind is capable of „forming”, analogous conceptions of unity („unities”), *not numbers*, are the specifically exact measures among all the notions the human mind is capable of forming. Conflated with „being”, St. Thomas, considered „unity” first to fall into the human intellect and to be understood in terms of „formal indivisibility” (unity of form), not in terms of the dimensive unity studied in mathematics. And, like „being”, St. Thomas considered „unity” to be said analogously to its subjects.

Strictly speaking, we human beings are incapable of knowing anything (*including numbers*, which are essentially and simultaneously „*more than one*” and „*limited pluralities*”, „*ordered multitudes*”) except as „existing unities, or ones”. We know everything, including numbers (the first of which is „two”: „two ones” conceived as „numerically-one two”) as existing „indivisible intelligibles”.

As Charles Bonaventure Crowley correctly understood, Aristotle and St. Thomas indicate that what makes any number to be a unit considered *per se* or a *per se* unit, is its last, or terminal, unit, which gives number its species and unity. „For just as things composed of matter and form are an *unum* (are one) through the form, from which both their unity and their species (nature) are constituted; so the last, or terminal, unit of any number is as a form, which gives both species and unity to that number”⁸.

That is, each number is a unity, a composite whole, constituted by a unity of order (or organizational unity, like an orchestra, or rowing team) „so that the ones which are prior to the last, or terminal, one are as ‘matter’, and the last, or terminal, one is as ‘form’, thus constituting number as an *unum* (one) *per se*, and making each number to be a specific terminated plurality of ones”, and a unique species of measure. Note should be made that since they are limits, and limits are qualities, Aristotle and St. Thomas considered forms to be qualities, or *virtual quantities*. This means that a proper understanding of the nature of number and the teaching of Aristotle and St. Thomas about it, demands knowledge of the nature of *virtual quantity*, a nature and principle regarding which Father Jaki appeared to have no knowledge!

Such being the case, *contra* Jaki, diverse, *evidently-known* first principles *analogously applied to diverse subject matters*, *not mathematical numbers applied to dimensive matter*, are the proximate, exact measurements of all being. Evidently-known, applied truths, not applied numbers, generate scientific exactness and measurement! Such being the case, the rest of the claims I have cited from Fr. Jaki are evidently false!

The different branches of science qualify for being called „exact” in the measure in which they *apply* evidently-known first principles (*measures*) to their respective subjects (what is meas-

⁸ Ch. B. Crowley, *Aristotelian-Thomistic Philosophy of Measure and the International System of Units (SI): Correlation of International System of Units with the Philosophy of Aristotle and St. Thomas*, ed. with a precept by Peter A. Redpath, Lanham, Md., New York, and London: University Press of America, 1996, p. 19.

ured): application of measures to what is measured essentially constituting the act of measurement. Numbers are ways of being one, unities. *For this reason only* are numbers measures; because, as Aristotle and St. Thomas state, „Unity is the measure of all things”⁹. Because unity measures everything, wholes are unities; and because mathematical numbers are mathematical wholes, *analogously*, mathematical numbers are measures. Hence, the claim that mathematics does not measure is absurd.

Since mathematical judgments measure mathematical subjects, mathematics is best taken as a science, not as a „form of logic”, as Jaki claims. And, since all science is, to the extent that it is a knowledge and a science, „exact”, mathematics is an exact science; but not as exact as metaphysics. Considered

in themselves as sciences, since metaphysics applies being and unity considered as indivision within a nature as its first principles, it applies the most evident of principles to everything that exists.

Finally, while, as Jaki says, the ancient Greeks might have failed precisely to understand the nature of physics, none of the leading ancient Greek philosophers would have committed such an egregious intellectual failure as to call physics, instead of theology, metaphysics, „the most important science”¹⁰. The fact that a Catholic-priest, physicist of Father Jaki’s intellectual greatness and orthodoxy could make such a profound error speaks volumes about the intellectual decay of contemporary Western civilization. God save us from our allies!

⁹ St. Thomas Aquinas, *Commentary on the Metaphysics*, by Thomas Aquinas, translated by J. P. Rowan, book 10, lesson. 2, Chicago 1961, html-edited by J. Kenny OP. <https://isidore.co/aquinas/english/Metaphysics10.htm> [date of access: 18.08.2022].

¹⁰ S.L. Jaki, *Science and Religion: A Primer*, p. 24.

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Małe błędy na początku: Stanley L. Jaki jako najlepszy obrońca chrześcijańskiej cywilizacji wolności i w pewnym sensie nieświadoma przeszkoda na jej drodze: perspektywa amerykańska/Gilsoniańska

Słowa kluczowe: filozofia, cywilizacja, chrześcijaństwo, Étienne Gilson

Prezentowany artykuł dotyczy tematu odejścia od filozofii rozumianej po Gilsonowsku jako bezinteresownego poznawania prawdy o otaczającym nas świecie oraz na wynikających z tego konsekwencjach (także w odniesieniu do nauczania filozofii). Artykuł wyraża przekonanie, że Gilsonowska koncepcja jedności doświadczenia filozoficznego ma swoje uzasadnienie, oraz że filozofię powinniśmy traktować jako punkt wyjścia i podstawę wszelkich nauk. Poglądy te są w artykule wyrażone w tonie pole-

micznym, gdyż sam artykuł jest polemiką z poglądami znanego filozofa, matematyka i teologa, Stanley'a Jaki, który uznaje, że współczesna fizyka jest obecnie jedyną – w sensie ścisłym – nauką. Autor, dyskutując z tym stanowiskiem, zwraca przede wszystkim uwagę na to, że wszelka nauka powinna być zorientowana mądrościowo (to znaczy powinna pytać o pierwsze przyczyny – *principia*) wszelkich składników dostrzeganej rzeczywistości.